

Study of primary phytochemicals from *Soymida febrifuga* leaves (Meliaceae)

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ABSTRACT

Soymida febrifuga, commonly called as Rohin used in various ethno medicinal practices. It has been reported that plant leaves is used for fever and diarrhea. Phytochemical extraction was carried out to test the presence of different phytochemicals in leaf of *Soymida febrifuga* from collected sample. Plants parts are dried and fine powder was subjected to different solvent extraction with soxhlet apparatus. The result for test showed presence of Alkaloids, Cardiac glycosides, Coumarins, Flavonoids, Glycosides, Phenols, Reducing sugars, Saponins, etc in Leaves extract, with three different solvent systems. Results reveals that the importance medicinal properties is due to the presence of these phyto-constituents which need to farther elaboration in future works to detect active ingredient for particular disease.

Keywords: *Phytochemicals, medicinal plants, ethno medicine, solvent system and Soymida febrifuga.*

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal properties of plants are very significance sence all time. From long ago plants are considered as a biosynthetic innovative, which can able to produce primary and secondary metabolites. Many primary metabolites such as, proteins carbohydrates, lipids and secondary metabolites like glycosides, alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, volatile oils etc., which are therapeutically useful in human beings and animals are obtained from these solar energy biosynthetic laboratories (Rekha Rajendran 2010 and Patil MB and Khan PA 2017).

Literature survey reveals that *Soymida febrifuga* is also having medicinal properties in folk medicines. The decoction of bark is given in fever, Bark used in the treatment of diarrhoea, dysentery and fever and also as a general tonic; decoction used in gargles, vaginal infections, rheumatism swellings and as enemata. One cup Decoction of stem bark is taken orally to cure “rakt pradar” (Adesida *et al.*, 1972 , Purushothaman *et al.*, 1977, Murali *et al.*, 1978 and Cowan MM 1999).

The information regarding presence of secondary metabolites in different part of *Soymida febrifuga* plant revels that very less work has been reported on leaves. These secondary metabolites have ability to alter biological processes, which can reduce the risk of chronic diseases in human beings such as diabetes. A large number of modern drugs have been isolated from natural sources which were used in traditional medicines such as tribal medicine in the form of crude drugs. Hence, it is essential to investigate phyto chemicals from leaf of *Soymida febrifuga* plants (Adesida *et al.*, 1971, Ashok *et al.*, 2012 and Ninad M *et al.*, 2013).

Plant samples for leaf of *Soymida febrifuga* was from Manu Devi hilly area from (Jalgaon) district (India).Collection, Identification and herbariums has been made by slandered protocols and samples are shed dried. The 25gm of obtained powdered from leaves sample was extracted with 150 ml of chloroform, methanol and Petroleum ether, using a Soxhlet extractor (60-80 °C) in subsequent 20 cycles. The extracts were concentrated with water bath at 60⁰ C then the semi-solid extracts were stored in refrigerator at 4⁰C for further use for preliminary phytochemical studies of Phenolic, Alkaloids, Carbohydrates, Tannins, Flavamoids, Steriods, Glycoside, Anthraquinones, Saponin Glycosides, and Amino acids has been taken out with reference to M. B. Patil and P. A. Khan (2017).

Fig. 1: *Soymida febrifuga*: Leaves and Soxhlet extractor

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The preliminary phytochemical tests were conducted on Petroleum ether, chloroform and methanol extracts of *Soymida febrifuga* leaves for qualitative analysis of various phytoconstituents using standard protocols as described by (Sofowora 1993, Trease and Evans 1989, Herborne 1973) the result was obtained shown in Table no. 1 (Varicola *et al.*, 2012.)

Table no. 1: Preliminary Phytochemical analysis of *Soymida febrifuga* Leaves in different solvents

Sr No	Phytochemicals Tests	Pet. ether	Chloroform	Methanol
1	Phenolics	+	+	++
2	Alkaloids	+	+	-
3	Carbohydrates	-	-	-
4	Tannins	+	+	+
5	Flavonoids	+	++	+++
6	Steroids	++	++	-
7	Triterpenoids	+	+	-
8	Glycoside	-	-	+
9	Anthraquinones	-	-	-
10	Saponin Glycosides	-	-	+
11	Amino acids	-	-	-

CONCLUSION

The current work for *Soymida febrifuga* found that there is very significance medicinal important of plants leaves extracts among different solvents. The present investigation shows very good and positive result for Flavonoids in pet ether followed by presence of, Phenols in same solvents. The current test show that Tannins, Flavonoids and Phenolics are shows their presence in all three solvents. Hence leaves of *Soymida febrifuga* having important primary metabolites in crude extract of said plant sample. As mention in above result table 1 there is a variation in the presence and absence of some phyto-constituents with respect to change in solvents and this due to polar and non polar property of solvent.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Author is so much thankful for the support and guidance of Dr. A. P. Rajput from K.K.Wagh Arts, Commerce, Science and Commerce College Nashik. Author is also thankful to the principal K.E.S.A.C.S College Kalwan for their valuable suggestion, encouragement and supports during the course of research work.

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